

Comparative Analysis of Random Distributions in Optimization Algorithms: A Study on Levy, Gamma, Tangent, Rayleigh, Weibull, Cauchy, Exponential, Log-Normal, and Chi-Square Distributions

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Abstract :

Random distributions play a crucial role in optimization algorithms, providing a means to introduce randomness and exploration in the search process. This paper presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of several random distributions, including Levy, Gamma, Tangent, Rayleigh, Weibull, Cauchy, Exponential, Log-Normal, and Chi-Square distributions, and their applications in optimization algorithms. The objective is to evaluate the suitability of these distributions for different optimization problems and shed light on their strengths and limitations. The paper provides an overview of each distribution, discusses their properties, and explores their utilization in optimization algorithms. Experimental results and analysis are presented to compare the performance of these distributions in various optimization scenarios. The findings of this study will assist researchers and practitioners in selecting appropriate random distributions for optimizing diverse problem domains.

Keywords: optimization algorithms, random distributions, exploitation, exploration, population optimization, flight distributions.

AMS Classification Numbers: 65K05, 90C59, 90C15, 65K10, 90C32

1. Introduction

Optimization algorithms play a pivotal role across diverse fields where finding optimal solutions within complex search spaces is essential. These algorithms can be broadly categorized into gradient-based, evolutionary, swarm intelligence-based, and other notable approaches. Gradient-based methods (e.g., gradient descent [1], conjugate gradient [2], Newton's method [3]) leverage gradient information to iteratively refine solutions. Evolutionary algorithms (EAs), such as genetic algorithms [4] and differential evolution [5], draw inspiration from biological evolution, operating on populations of solutions that undergo selection, recombination, and mutation. Swarm intelligence techniques, including particle swarm optimization (PSO) [6] and ant colony optimization (ACO) [7], model the decentralized, collaborative behavior of natural systems to guide the search process. Other important methods like simulated annealing (SA) [8] introduce probabilistic mechanisms for escaping local optima, while tabu search [9] employs memory structures to prevent revisiting previously explored regions of the search space.

The choice of optimization algorithm is heavily influenced by factors such as the problem's nature (continuous, discrete, combinatorial), the objective function's complexity, and the presence of constraints. Additionally, researchers must often navigate trade-offs between solution quality, computational expense, and convergence speed.

A key consideration in algorithm design is how to efficiently explore the search space while effectively exploiting promising regions. Pure exploitation runs the risk of getting trapped in local optima, while undirected exploration slows convergence. Achieving the right balance between these two objectives, known as the exploration-exploitation tradeoff, is crucial for algorithm performance.

In the field of optimization algorithms, it is important to understand the effects and implications of utilizing random distributions. Different random distributions can play a crucial role in optimization algorithms. They can affect the exploration and exploitation trade-off, the convergence speed, and the overall performance of the algorithm. Understanding the effects of different random distributions in optimization algorithms is crucial as it can impact the exploration-exploitation trade-off, convergence speed, and overall performance of the algorithm. Several common random distributions used in optimization algorithms include uniform distribution, normal distribution, exponential distribution, and others. Each distribution has its own characteristics and properties that can influence the behavior of the optimization algorithm. Stochastic components strategically introduced into the search process can offer significant benefits:

- **Initialization:** Randomly initializing the starting points of an algorithm or a population of solutions (in evolutionary or swarm-based methods) helps ensure a broader exploration of the search space, increasing the likelihood of uncovering global optima rather than converging prematurely to local ones [10].
- **Exploration and Diversification:** Incorporating randomness into an algorithm's search mechanisms promotes exploration of diverse areas, helping to avoid getting trapped in local optima [11]. Techniques like random mutations in evolutionary algorithms or stochastic velocity updates in particle swarm optimization maintain solution diversity [12].
- **Escaping Local Optima:** Algorithms like simulated annealing employ probabilistic acceptance of temporarily worse solutions. This allows them to "jump" out of local optima, potentially leading to globally better solutions in later stages of the search [13].
- **Robustness:** Random elements can make algorithms more robust to variations in problem characteristics or noise within the objective function evaluation [14].
- **Adaptability to Complex Landscapes:** In complex, multimodal optimization landscapes, randomness can facilitate the search process by allowing algorithms to traverse regions with poor solutions in pursuit of better areas of the search space [15].

However, not all forms of randomness are equally suited for different optimization problems and algorithmic approaches. The properties of the underlying random distribution have a significant impact on how it influences exploration versus exploitation. Distributions with heavier tails facilitate large variations favoring exploration, while others concentrate variations locally around the best solutions to exploit promising regions.

This necessitates a thorough understanding of various probability distributions that can be leveraged for algorithmic randomness. Their characteristics must be mapped to how they shape the exploration-exploitation behavior. Careful choice and design of random distributions tailored to optimization problems can greatly impact convergence and solution quality. Therefore, this work aims to provide insights into the properties and applications of several major random distributions commonly used in optimization algorithms. A comparative study will shed light on their effects and suitability for diverse scenarios, guiding practitioners in selecting appropriate distributions. This enhances algorithm design and paves the way for improved optimization solutions.

This paper focuses on the utilization of various random distributions in optimization algorithms. Specifically, we will delve into the properties and applications of the following distributions: Levy [16], Gamma [17], Tangent [18], Rayleigh [19], Weibull [20,21], Cauchy [22], Exponential [23], Log-Normal [24], and Chi-Square [25]. These distributions possess unique characteristics that can influence the behavior and performance of optimization algorithms.

The objective of this study is twofold. Firstly, it aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of each random distribution, exploring their mathematical properties and characteristics. This understanding will facilitate an informed selection of appropriate distributions for specific optimization problems. Secondly, the study aims to analyze the impact of these random distributions on algorithm performance. By conducting experimental evaluations and comparative analyses, we can assess the strengths, limitations, and suitability of each distribution for different optimization scenarios.

By delving into the use of random distributions in optimization algorithms, this paper aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by providing insights into the role of randomness in optimization processes. The findings and analyses presented herein will aid researchers and practitioners in making informed decisions when selecting and designing optimization algorithms for diverse problem domains.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the different distributions. Section 3 discusses random distributions for optimization. Section 4 presents the comparative results and discussion. Finally, we conclude in Section 5.

2. Different random distributions used in optimization

In this section, we present the most used distributions in optimization: Levy, Gamma, Rayleigh, Weibull, Cauchy, Exponential, Log-Normal, and Chi-Square distributions.

2.1 Levy Distribution

are a type of random walk where the step lengths have a stable distribution, which is a probability distribution with heavy tails. This means that there is a higher probability of taking long jumps compared to a normal random walk. This property makes Levy flights well-suited for searching large and complex spaces, as they can efficiently explore both local and distant regions. Levy flights are named after French mathematician Paul Pierre Lévy, who studied them in the early 20th century. They have been found to be a good model for the movement of animals, such as albatrosses and foraging ants, as well as for the spread of epidemics and financial markets. The probability density function (PDF) of the Levy distribution is given by:

$$f(x; \mu, c) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi c^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2c^2}(x - \mu)^2\right) \quad (1)$$

where:

- x is the random variable,
- μ is the location parameter (the location of the distribution's peak),
- c is the scale parameter (controls the spread or width of the distribution),
- π is the mathematical constant pi, and
- $\exp$ denotes the exponential function.

This formula represents the Levy distribution when x is greater than or equal to μ . For $x < \mu$, the distribution is often defined as zero or undefined, depending on the context.

It's important to note that the Levy distribution does not have a finite variance, and its heavy tails make it behave differently from many other common probability distributions, such as the normal distribution. Additionally, the Levy distribution is characterized by its stable distribution property, meaning that if you sum a large number of independent and identically distributed random variables from a Levy distribution, properly scaled and centered, the resulting distribution will also be a Levy distribution. Here are some of the key properties of Levy flights:

- They are scale-free, meaning that they look the same regardless of the scale at which they are observed.
- They are self-similar, meaning that any small part of a Levy flight path looks like the whole path.
- They have infinite variance, which means that the average squared step length is infinite.

2.2 Gamma Distribution

The Gamma distribution is a continuous probability distribution that is widely used in statistics to model the time until an event occurs. It's also commonly used in various fields such as physics, engineering, and finance. The distribution is characterized by two parameters: shape parameter (α) and rate parameter (β). The probability density function (PDF) of the Gamma distribution is given by:

$$f(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\beta^\alpha} x^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{x}{\beta}} \quad (2)$$

where:

- (x) is the random variable,
- (α) (shape parameter) is a positive real number,
- (β) (rate parameter) is a positive real number,
- ($\Gamma(\alpha)$) is the Gamma function evaluated at (α),
- (e) is the base of the natural logarithm, and

The shape parameter (α) controls the shape of the distribution, with larger values resulting in distributions that are more concentrated around the mean. The rate parameter (β) determines the rate at which the distribution decays, with smaller values leading to faster decay.

The Gamma distribution can take on a variety of shapes depending on the values of its parameters. When ($\alpha = 1$), the Gamma distribution reduces to the exponential distribution. Additionally, when (α) is an integer, the Gamma distribution can be interpreted as the sum of (α) independent exponentially distributed random variables.

2.3 Rayleigh Distribution

The Rayleigh distribution is a continuous probability distribution used to model the magnitudes of 2D vectors, such as wind speeds, wave heights, or the distribution of random variables representing the magnitude of the sum of two independent, identically distributed Gaussian random variables. It's named after Lord Rayleigh, a British scientist known for his work in physics and engineering. The probability density function (PDF) of the Rayleigh distribution is given by:

$$f(x; \sigma) = \frac{x}{\sigma^2} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (3)$$

where:

- (x) is the random variable representing the magnitude of the vector,
- (σ) is the scale parameter (a positive real number),
- (e) is the base of the natural logarithm.

The scale parameter - (σ) controls the spread or width of the distribution. Larger values of - (σ) result in distributions with wider peaks and heavier tails. The mean and variance of the Rayleigh distribution are given by:

$$\text{Mean} = \sigma \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Variance} = \sigma^2 \left(1 - \frac{2}{\pi}\right) \quad (5)$$

The Rayleigh distribution is often used in situations where the underlying process involves the addition of independent random variables, each with the same distribution (typically Gaussian). For example, in wireless communications, the magnitude of the received signal, affected by noise and multipath fading, can often be modeled using the Rayleigh distribution. Additionally, it's worth noting that the Rayleigh distribution is a special case of the Weibull distribution when the shape parameter is equal to 2.

2.4 Weibull Distribution

The Weibull distribution is a versatile continuous probability distribution widely used in reliability engineering, life data analysis, and survival analysis to model time-to-failure data. It's named after Waloddi Weibull, a Swedish engineer, who introduced it in 1951. The probability density function (PDF) of the Weibull distribution is given by:

$$f(x; \lambda, k) = \frac{k}{\lambda} \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{k-1} e^{-(x/\lambda)^k} \quad (6)$$

where:

- (x) is the random variable representing time-to-failure or other non-negative quantities,
- (λ) (lambda) is the scale parameter (a positive real number),
- (k) (kappa) is the shape parameter (a positive real number),
- (e) is the base of the natural logarithm.

The shape parameter (k) determines the shape of the distribution. When ($k > 1$), the Weibull distribution is right-skewed, with a long tail to the right, resembling the exponential distribution. When ($k = 1$), the Weibull distribution reduces to the exponential distribution. When ($k < 1$), the distribution is left-skewed, with a long tail to the left. The scale parameter (λ) controls the scale or characteristic lifetime of the distribution. Larger values of (λ) correspond to longer expected lifetimes. The mean and variance of the Weibull distribution are given by:

$$\text{Mean} = \lambda \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Variance} = \lambda^2 \left[\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{2}{k}\right) - \left(\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)\right)^2 \right] \quad (8)$$

where $\Gamma(x)$ is the Gamma function. The Weibull distribution is highly flexible and can model a wide range of failure behaviors, making it a valuable tool in reliability engineering and survival analysis. It's commonly used to analyze time-to-failure data, such as the lifetimes of mechanical components, electronic devices, or biological organisms. Additionally, it's also applied in various other fields, including hydrology, finance, and wind energy.

2.5 Cauchy Distribution

The Cauchy distribution, also known as the Lorentz distribution, is a continuous probability distribution named after the French mathematician Augustin Cauchy. It is notable for its heavy tails, which means it has a higher probability of extreme deviations from the mean compared to many other probability distributions, such as the normal distribution. The probability density function (PDF) of the Cauchy distribution is given by:

$$f(x; x_0, \gamma) = \frac{1}{\pi\gamma \left[1 + \left(\frac{x-x_0}{\gamma} \right)^2 \right]} \quad (9)$$

where:

- (x) is the random variable,
- (x_0) is the location parameter (the median of the distribution),
- (γ) (Gamma) is the scale parameter (a positive real number),
- (π) is the mathematical constant pi.

The Cauchy distribution does not have a defined mean or variance due to its heavy tails. However, its median is (x_0) , and the interquartile range is (2γ) . The Cauchy distribution is symmetric about its median (x_0) , with tails that extend infinitely in both directions. Despite its lack of finite moments (mean and variance), the Cauchy distribution arises naturally in various contexts, including physics, finance, and statistics. In physics, it describes resonances and particle decay widths, while in finance, it's used to model price changes and extreme market movements. In statistics, it serves as a counterexample to illustrate situations where the sample mean may not converge to the population mean due to heavy tails.

2.6 Exponential Distribution

The Exponential distribution is a continuous probability distribution that models the time between events in a Poisson process, where events occur at a constant average rate and are independent of the time since the last event. It's widely used in reliability engineering, queueing theory, and survival analysis. The probability density function (PDF) of the Exponential distribution is given by:

$$f(x; \lambda) = \lambda e^{-\lambda x} \quad (10)$$

where:

- (x) is the random variable representing the time between events,
- (λ) (lambda) is the rate parameter (a positive real number),
- (e) is the base of the natural logarithm.

The rate parameter (λ) represents the average rate of event occurrences per unit of time. The higher the value of (λ), the more events are expected to occur in a given time interval. The mean and variance of the Exponential distribution are given by:

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \quad (12)$$

The Exponential distribution is memoryless, meaning that the time since the last event does not affect the probability of an event occurring in the future. This property makes it particularly useful in modeling processes where events occur randomly and independently over time. Applications of the Exponential distribution include modeling lifetimes of components in reliability engineering, inter-arrival times in queueing systems, and survival times in survival analysis. It's also commonly used in Bayesian statistics as a conjugate prior for the rate parameter of a Poisson distribution.

2.7 Log-Normal Distribution

The Log-Normal distribution models situations where the logarithm of the variable is normally distributed. The probability density function is given by:

$$f(x; \mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{x\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(\log(x)-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (13)$$

where (μ) and (σ) are the mean and standard deviation of the logarithm of the variable. The mean and variance of the Log-Normal distribution are:

$$\text{Mean} = e^{\mu + \frac{\sigma^2}{2}} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Variance} = (e^{\sigma^2} - 1)e^{2\mu + \sigma^2} \quad (15)$$

This distribution is used in fields like finance, environmental studies, and reliability engineering to model skewed data with a long tail.

2.8 Chi-Square Distribution

The Chi-Square distribution is a continuous probability distribution that arises in statistics, particularly in the context of hypothesis testing and confidence interval estimation. It's derived from the sum of squared standard normal random variables and is widely used in various statistical tests, such as the chi-square test for independence, goodness-of-fit tests, and tests of variance. The Chi-Square distribution with (k) degrees of freedom is denoted as $(\chi^2(k))$. The degrees of freedom parameter (k) determines the shape of the distribution. The probability density function (PDF) of the Chi-Square distribution is given by:

$$f(x; k) = \frac{1}{2^{k/2}\Gamma(\frac{k}{2})} x^{\frac{k}{2}-1} e^{-\frac{x}{2}} \quad (16)$$

where:

- (x) is the random variable,
- (k) is the degrees of freedom parameter (a positive integer),
- (Γ) is the Gamma function.

The Gamma function $(\Gamma(k/2))$ is defined as:

$$\Gamma(k/2) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{\frac{k}{2}-1} e^{-t} dt \quad (17)$$

The mean and variance of the Chi-Square distribution are given by:

$$\text{Mean} = k \quad (18)$$

$$\text{Variance} = 2k \quad (19)$$

The Chi-Square distribution is positively skewed and becomes more symmetric as the degrees of freedom increase. It's often used in hypothesis testing to assess the goodness of fit between observed and expected frequencies, test for independence in contingency tables, and test for variance in populations. In practical applications, the Chi-Square distribution is frequently encountered in fields such as biology, psychology, economics, and engineering, where statistical analyses involve comparing observed data to expected distributions or assessing variability within datasets.

3. Random Distributions in Optimization:

Traditional optimization algorithms can struggle with complex problems that have non-convex, noisy, or multidimensional landscapes. Deterministic methods like gradient

descent are prone to getting stuck in local optima or being misled by noise. This is where stochastic optimization shines. By introducing randomness into the search process, stochastic algorithms are able to escape local traps and more thoroughly explore the solution space.

There are a few key ways randomness can be implemented. Candidate solutions can be sampled from a probability distribution, allowing the algorithm to probe different regions of the search space. Alternatively, the distribution can guide the search direction by generating steps of random magnitude and direction. Adaptive control further improves results - the distribution parameters are adjusted over time based on optimization progress, balancing exploration to find new possibilities with exploitation to refine promising areas.

The benefits of stochastic optimization are significant. The randomness enhances exploration, helping algorithms avoid local optima to potentially locate the global solution. It also averages out noise, leading to more robust solutions for complex, noisy problems. Some distributions even enable efficient parallelization, where multiple runs explore concurrently to accelerate convergence.

However, choosing the right distribution is critical. Performance depends on factors like the problem landscape characteristics (multi-modality, noise, dimensionality) as well as the algorithm's needs. The distribution must also strike a balance between fast convergence and stable search behavior. By carefully considering these elements, stochastic optimization opens the door to more generally applicable and effective algorithms. The randomness counteracts real-world challenges to power robust solutions for complex optimization problems.

3.1 Using randomness in metaheuristics

Optimization algorithms are computational methods used to find the best possible solution to a given problem. These algorithms iteratively explore the search space, evaluating candidate solutions based on an objective function or a set of constraints. Various optimization algorithms, such as evolutionary algorithms, swarm intelligence algorithms, and local search algorithms, have been developed to tackle different types of optimization problems. Randomness is woven into the fabric of metaheuristic algorithms. It serves several key purposes:

- **Exploration:** Randomness facilitates a wider exploration of the search space, helping the algorithm discover potentially better regions it might not have reached deterministically.
- **Exploitation:** Randomness helps fine-tune promising solutions within a local area of the search space:
- **Initialization:** Random distributions are often used to generate an initial population or set of solutions. These random solutions provide a diverse starting point, allowing the algorithm to explore different regions of the search space from the beginning.
- **Random Moves:** During the optimization process, algorithms make random moves or perturbations in the search space. Random distributions help

determine the magnitude and direction of these moves, allowing the algorithm to explore new areas and escape local optima.

- **Diversity Maintenance:** Random distributions contribute to maintaining diversity within the population. By introducing randomness, the algorithm can explore and preserve diverse solutions, preventing premature convergence to suboptimal regions.
- **Local Search:** Random distributions are often used in combination with local search techniques. After exploring different regions, the algorithm can concentrate its efforts on promising areas by using random distributions to guide the search towards solutions with better fitness values.
- **Sampling and Estimation:** In stochastic optimization or uncertainty-based problems, random distributions are used for sampling values or generating scenarios. These samples allow the algorithm to estimate objective function values and make informed decisions, contributing to exploitation of the search space.

The power of randomness becomes even clearer when we look at specific examples. Evolutionary algorithms, like genetic algorithms, use randomness to create initial populations and introduce variation during the "breeding" process. This exploration and diversification increase the chances of finding optimal solutions. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) Inspired by the swarming behavior of birds, PSO utilizes random distributions to update the velocity of particles searching for the optimal solution. Particles move based on their own inertia, the best solution found by the swarm, and a random component. This random element allows particles to explore new regions and avoid getting stuck in local optima Simulated annealing mimics the cooling process of metals, using random moves to escape local optima and explore the search space more broadly. Finally, Monte Carlo methods, widely used in problems with uncertainty, leverage random distributions to sample values and estimate objective functions, guiding the search towards better solutions.

Each random distributions offers unique characteristics that make them suitable for different optimization problems and contexts. Understanding their properties helps in selecting the appropriate distribution to enhance the performance of optimization algorithms, balancing exploration and exploitation effectively.

Levy distributions have heavy tails which can facilitate large jumps in the search space, aiding exploration of new areas. However, many small jumps may be needed to exploit promising regions. Gamma distributions have shape parameters to control dispersion. Higher shape leads to exploitation near best solutions, while lower shape favors broader exploration. Tangent distributions sample around the current best solution, focusing exploitation. Adding occasional long jumps can enhance exploration. Rayleigh distributions concentrate samples near the origin, favoring exploitation over exploration of distant regions. Weibull distributions' shape parameter controls concentration level. Higher shape samples cluster near best solution, exploiting locally. Lower shape scatters samples more widely. Cauchy distributions have heavy tails like Levy, favoring major jumps and exploration over gradual local search. Precise exploitation may require many iterations. Exponential distributions explore extensively at first but concentrate exponentially near best

solution over time, gradually shifting emphasis to exploitation. Log-normal distributions can generate both small local variations and occasional long jumps, balancing exploration and exploitation based on standard deviation. Chi-square distributions sample most frequently near the origin compared to other tails, pushing the focus more towards local exploitation than distant exploration. The following table (table 1) captures how the properties of each distribution influence the balance between exploring new areas and exploiting known good solutions in optimization problems.

Table 1. Properties of random distributions

Distribution	Properties	Exploration	Exploitation
Levy	Heavy tails, higher probability of long jumps, infinite variance	Facilitates large jumps, enabling exploration of distant areas	Many small jumps required for effective local search, less efficient local exploitation
Tangent	Samples around the current best solution	Generally, focuses on local search, can be adjusted for exploration with occasional long jumps	Primarily favors exploitation around the current best solution
Gamma	Shape (α) and rate (β) parameters, shape controls dispersion	Lower shape (α) favors broad exploration	Higher shape (α) results in more concentrated sampling, enhancing local exploitation
Rayleigh	Concentrates samples near the origin, models magnitudes of 2D vectors	Less effective for exploring distant regions	Favors local exploitation, suitable for fine-tuning around the current best solution
Weibull	Scale (λ) and shape (k) parameters, shape controls concentration	Lower shape ($k < 1$) scatters samples more widely, enhancing exploration	Higher shape ($k > 1$) clusters samples near best solutions, improving local exploitation
Cauchy	Heavy tails, no defined mean or variance	Favors major jumps, effective for exploration	Precise exploitation may require many iterations due to frequent large jumps

Exponential	Models time between events in a Poisson process, memoryless property	Initially promotes extensive exploration due to exponential decay	Gradually shifts emphasis to exploitation, concentrating near the best solution over time
Log-Normal	Generates values based on log of a normally distributed variable, capable of both small and large jumps	Standard deviation controls balance; larger deviations facilitate exploration	Smaller deviations favor local exploitation, adaptable based on current search needs
Chi-Square	Sum of squared standard normal variables, positively skewed	Less focus on distant exploration as samples are more frequently near the origin	Pushes towards local exploitation, suitable for fine-tuning around current best solutions

3.2. Evaluation of the effectiveness of random distributions

determining the effectiveness of random distributions in promoting exploration and exploitation in optimization algorithms involves empirical evaluation and comparative analysis. Researchers can employ several techniques to assess the impact of random distributions on algorithm performance. Here are some commonly used approaches:

- **Experimental Evaluation:** Researchers can conduct experiments by implementing and running optimization algorithms using different random distributions. The algorithms can be executed on a set of benchmark problems with known optima or real-world problems. The performance metrics, such as convergence speed, solution quality, and success rate, can be measured and compared across different random distributions. This empirical evaluation provides insights into how each distribution affects exploration and exploitation.
- **Sensitivity Analysis:** Researchers can perform sensitivity analysis to study the influence of random distributions on optimization algorithm behavior. By systematically varying the parameters of a specific random distribution and observing the resulting changes in algorithm performance, researchers can evaluate the impact of each distribution on exploration and exploitation. Sensitivity analysis helps identify the parameter settings that lead to better exploration or exploitation capabilities.
- **Comparative Studies:** Comparative studies involve comparing the performance of optimization algorithms using different random distributions. Researchers can conduct side-by-side comparisons on the same set of benchmark problems or real-world applications. Statistical tests, such as t-tests or ANOVA, can be applied to determine if significant performance differences exist between the

algorithms. Comparative studies provide insights into the relative effectiveness of different random distributions in promoting exploration and exploitation.

- **Visualization and Analysis of Search Trajectories:** Researchers can visualize and analyze the search trajectories of optimization algorithms using different random distributions. This involves plotting the progress of the algorithm in the search space and observing how it explores and exploits different regions. Visual analysis can provide insights into the exploration-exploitation trade-off and the impact of random distributions on the search behavior of the algorithm.
- **Theoretical Analysis:** Theoretical analysis can be employed to study the properties and characteristics of random distributions and their impact on exploration and exploitation. Researchers can examine the mathematical properties of distributions, such as variance, skewness, kurtosis, or tail behavior, and their implications for optimization algorithms. Theoretical analysis helps establish a foundational understanding of how different random distributions influence exploration and exploitation.

By using these approaches, researchers can gather empirical evidence, insights, and statistical validation regarding the effectiveness of different random distributions in promoting exploration and exploitation. It is important to conduct rigorous and comprehensive evaluations across multiple problems and performance metrics to draw reliable conclusions about the impact of random distributions on optimization algorithm behavior.

4. Comparative Analysis and Discussion

To assess the efficacy of various distributions in balancing exploration and exploitation within optimization algorithms, we implemented diverse flight operators based on these distributions in MATLAB. Each flight operator dictates how a potential solution (or "agent") moves through the search space. The following table summarizes the step computation for each implemented operator.

Table 2. step computation for each for each flight

Flight operator	Step computation	comment
levy	$\beta=3/2,$ $\sigma=(\Gamma(1+\beta)*\sin(\pi*\beta/2)/(\Gamma((1+\beta)/2)*\beta*2^{((\beta-1)/2)}))^{1/\beta};$ $u=\text{randn}(1,\text{dim})*\sigma;$ $v=\text{randn}(1,\text{dim});$ $\text{step}=u./\text{abs}(v).^{(1/\beta)};$	Lévy flights are characterized by their heavy-tailed distribution, allowing for both small and large steps. This makes them effective for exploration as they can potentially escape local optima by making large jumps. The parameter β controls the heaviness of the tail, with $\beta=1.5$ often used in practice. The computation involves generating two normally distributed random numbers u and v and using them to compute the step size based on the Lévy distribution
Gamma	if rand ≤ 0.3 $\alpha = 1$ $\sigma = \text{sign}(\text{rand}(1,d)-0.5)*\text{randg}(\alpha,[1 d]);$ else $\alpha = 1$ $\text{step}=(10/d)*\text{sign}(\text{rand}(1,d)-0.5)*\text{norm}(\text{randn}(1,d))^{1/2};$	The Gamma distribution is versatile due to its shape parameter. When $\alpha=1$, it reduces to the exponential distribution. The step computation involves a probabilistic decision: with 30% probability, a gamma-distributed random number is generated, otherwise, a normal distribution-based

	<pre> sigma=step.*randg(alpha,[1 d]); end d: problem dimension </pre>	<p>step is scaled by a Gamma random variable. This dual approach balances exploration and exploitation.</p>
Tangent	<pre> if rand <=0.25%0.3 step= sign(rand(1,d)-0.5).*tan(rand*pi/2); else teta=rand(1,d)*pi/2.1; step=sign(rand(1,d)-0.5).*tan(teta); end </pre>	<p>The Tangent distribution provides a unique approach by using the tangent function to generate steps. This can result in very large or very small steps, controlled by the angle θ</p>
Rayleigh	<pre> sigma =5*rand*rand step=0.5*sign(rand(1,d)-0.5).*raylrnd(sigma,1,d) </pre>	<p>The Rayleigh distribution is effective in generating smooth, bell-shaped steps. The scale parameter σ is randomly determined, influencing the spread of the distribution. This approach is suitable for local search phases of optimization, providing moderate exploration without large jumps.</p>
Weibull	<pre> if rand <=0.25 lambda =1 k=1 step=sign(rand(1,d)-0.5).*wblrnd(lambda,k,[1 d]); else lambda =0.5 k=0.1+rand step= sign(rand(1,d)-0.5).*wblrnd(lambda,k,[1 d]); end </pre>	<p>The Weibull distribution, with its shape and scale parameters (k and λ), offers flexibility. The shape parameter k influences the distribution's tail, while λ affects the scale. The probabilistic choice between two sets of parameters allows for different step sizes, balancing between exploration and exploitation</p>
Cauchy	<pre> delta = tan(pi * (rand(1,d) - 0.5)); step= 0.5*delta </pre>	<p>The Cauchy distribution, known for its heavy tails, can produce very large steps, aiding in escaping local optima. The step computation involves generating a Cauchy-distributed random number δ and scaling it. However, its heavy-tailed</p>
Exp	<pre> lambda = 0.5; step = -log(1 - rand(1, d)) / lambda; step=sign(rand(1,d)-0.5).*step; </pre>	<p>The Exponential distribution is characterized by a single rate parameter λ, which controls the scale of the steps. The computation uses the inverse transform sampling method to generate exponentially distributed random numbers. The step size generated is then randomly assigned a direction (positive or negative) to ensure balanced exploration in both directions. This distribution is effective for moderate exploration, offering a good balance between small and large steps</p>
Log	<pre> mu = 0; lambda = 0.5; step = lognrnd(mu, lambda, d, 1); step=randn(1, d)*step; </pre>	<p>The Log-Normal distribution, derived from the exponential of a normally distributed variable, is useful for generating positive-only steps that can vary widely in scale. The parameters μ and λ control the mean and standard deviation of the underlying normal distribution. The step size is generated from the Log-Normal distribution and then scaled by a standard normal random variable to introduce variability in</p>

		direction and magnitude. This method can produce significant exploration with a tendency towards larger steps due to the distribution's positive skewness.
Chi2	<pre> k = 2; step = chi2rnd(k, 1, d); step=randn(1, d).*step; </pre>	The Chi-Squared distribution, commonly used in statistical contexts, is defined by its degrees of freedom k. For step computation, k is set to 2, which produces a distribution with moderate variability. The generated step sizes, which are always positive, are then scaled by a standard normal random variable to introduce both direction and additional variability. This distribution is effective in generating steps that are more exploratory than a normal distribution but less extreme than heavy-tailed distributions like Cauchy or Lévy.

To test the exploitation and the exploration capacities of each distribution flight, we have implemented simple population optimization algorithm. The population size is set to 20 and the number of iterations is set to 10000*D where D is the problem dimension. Initially, we focused on evaluating the exploitation capacity of the flight distributions. Each solution underwent refinement using the equation:

$$X=X+\alpha.*(Best_X-X) \quad (20)$$

Where X is the current solution, Best_X is the best current solution, α is a step generated by the flight distribution.

The purpose of the exploitation test phase is to evaluate how effectively different flight distributions refine and exploit the solutions obtained during the optimization process. In this phase, the focus is on improving the quality of solutions by iteratively refining them towards optimality. The exploitation test assesses the ability of each distribution to make incremental improvements to the solutions based on local information, such as the best solution found so far. By conducting the exploitation test, researchers can understand how well each distribution exploits the search space to converge towards optimal or near-optimal solutions.

In the second phase, we tested the exploration capacity by using the following equation:

$$X=X+0.5*\alpha \quad (21)$$

Where α is random vector generated by a flight distribution.

The purpose of the exploration test phase is to evaluate how effectively different flight distributions facilitate the exploration of the solution space. This phase aims to assess the ability of each distribution to generate diverse solutions by introducing randomness into the search process. By conducting the exploration test, researchers can understand how well each distribution explores the search space, identifies promising regions, and avoids getting stuck in local optima. Overall, this phase helps in determining the distribution's capability to navigate through the solution space and uncover potentially optimal solutions.

4.1. Result Discussion

The provided tables 3, 4, 5 and 6 present the mean results of exploiting different flight distributions in population optimization algorithms across two scenarios: function optimization in 10D and 20D spaces, based on the CEC2022 benchmark functions [26]. We discuss the effectiveness of different flights in terms of exploitation and exploration. The mean results provide insights into how effectively each flight distribution exploits the solution space to improve the quality of solutions. Lower values in the mean results generally indicate better exploitation capacity, as they suggest that the algorithm converges to better solutions. The provided tables present the mean results of exploring different flight distributions in population optimization algorithms across two scenarios: function optimization in 10D and 20D spaces, based on the CEC2022 benchmark functions. Let's analyze the implications of these results.

In the exploitation assessment, in 10D test function (table 3), levy, Tangent, Rayleigh, Weibull, and Gamma consistently demonstrate excellent exploitation capabilities across most functions. They achieve very small objective function values (often close to zero or very small positive numbers), suggesting they can effectively refine solutions towards optimality. Exponential and Log-Normal perform poorly in this experiment, likely due to their tendency for larger, less controlled movements.

Table 3. Mean results of 10D cec2022 function for exploitation distribution flights

	Levy	Gamma	Tangent	Rayleigh	Weibull	Cauchy	Exp	Log	Chi2
Friedman rank	4	5	3	2	1	6	9	8	7
CEC1	9.001E-08	1.025E+00	1.705E-14	4.610E-06	5.684E-15	2.228E-05	7.065E+02	3.790E-15	4.451E+01
CEC2	4.727E+00	3.402E+00	2.628E+00	2.839E+00	1.325E+00	4.862E+00	3.489E+00	7.376E+00	2.566E+00
CEC3	4.169E-14	6.063E-14	7.579E-14	6.063E-14	3.411E-14	6.442E-14	6.899E-02	1.911E-04	2.664E-07
CEC4	2.383E+01	2.583E+01	1.364E+01	2.032E+01	1.705E+01	2.556E+01	3.763E+01	1.752E+01	2.875E+01
CEC5	8.953E-03	1.351E-07	1.359E-01	2.984E-03	5.313E-02	1.249E-04	1.009E+00	1.350E-01	2.101E-05
CEC6	9.476E+02	1.395E+03	3.262E+02	8.287E+02	6.195E+02	8.569E+02	2.209E+03	1.185E+03	1.892E+03
CEC7	1.671E+00	1.933E+00	7.104E+00	5.396E-01	2.200E+00	1.539E+00	3.954E+00	2.767E+00	1.513E+00
CEC8	1.359E+01	1.591E+01	1.118E+01	1.623E+01	1.860E+01	1.453E+01	2.401E+01	1.695E+01	1.823E+01
CEC9	2.293E+02	2.293E+02	2.293E+02	2.293E+02	2.293E+02	2.293E+02	2.293E+02	2.293E+02	2.293E+02
CEC10	1.046E+02	1.084E+02	1.079E+02	1.003E+02	1.342E+02	1.185E+02	1.006E+02	1.556E+02	1.045E+02
CEC11	1.538E+01	3.711E+00	2.003E+01	1.000E+01	3.025E+01	5.016E+00	1.151E+00	9.242E+01	2.708E-06
CEC12	1.642E+02	1.636E+02	1.661E+02	1.639E+02	1.647E+02	1.632E+02	1.647E+02	1.654E+02	1.638E+02

In 20D test functions (table 4), Weibull distribution ranks first in Friedman test, achieving the lowest objective function values across many functions. This suggests it excels at refining solutions towards the optimum in higher-dimensional spaces. Log-Normal, Rayleigh, and Tangent show competitive performance on several functions, particularly, where they outperform Weibull. Gamma (Rank 7) and Chi-Squared (Rank 8): These distributions show less consistent results, with some good performance on certain functions but struggling on others. Exponential (Rank 9): This distribution consistently underperforms in exploitation, often resulting in much larger objective function values compared to the top performers. Its tendency for larger jumps might hinder its ability to refine solutions effectively.

Table 4. Mean results of 20D cec2022 function for exploitation distribution flights

	Levy	Gamma	Tangent	Rayleigh	Weibull	Cauchy	Exp	Log	Chi2
Friedman rank	5	7	4	3	1	6	9	2	8
CEC1	2.329E+03	4.261E+03	7.315E+02	2.197E+03	8.487E+01	3.512E+03	1.370E+04	1.482E+02	8.311E+03
CEC2	5.137E+01	5.117E+01	5.224E+01	5.372E+01	5.094E+01	5.223E+01	1.733E+02	4.247E+01	6.446E+01
CEC3	4.842E-07	7.890E-04	7.637E-02	2.732E-12	1.251E-13	3.506E-03	1.474E+01	6.708E-03	2.585E+00
CEC4	1.067E+02	1.143E+02	7.088E+01	1.035E+02	1.004E+02	1.124E+02	1.334E+02	1.052E+02	1.223E+02
CEC5	1.328E+00	1.627E+00	2.771E+01	4.406E-01	8.722E-01	7.719E-01	7.759E+02	1.972E+00	1.421E+02
CEC6	7.564E+03	1.205E+05	3.169E+03	4.983E+04	1.492E+04	6.239E+04	2.387E+06	5.893E+03	5.838E+05
CEC7	3.711E+01	3.866E+01	3.117E+01	4.117E+01	3.899E+01	3.774E+01	5.796E+01	3.515E+01	5.087E+01
CEC8	3.453E+01	3.673E+01	2.580E+01	3.393E+01	3.340E+01	3.616E+01	4.337E+01	3.333E+01	3.840E+01
CEC9	1.808E+02	1.808E+02	1.808E+02	1.808E+02	1.808E+02	1.808E+02	1.976E+02	1.808E+02	1.833E+02
CEC10	1.148E+02	1.062E+02	1.272E+02	1.048E+02	1.169E+02	1.024E+02	1.031E+02	1.342E+02	1.163E+02
CEC11	3.267E+02	2.967E+02	3.400E+02	3.133E+02	3.233E+02	3.333E+02	1.069E+03	2.967E+02	3.505E+02
CEC12	2.498E+02	2.438E+02	2.590E+02	2.469E+02	2.468E+02	2.452E+02	2.976E+02	2.503E+02	2.683E+02

In the Exploration Evaluation (table 5 and 6), Weibull (Rank 1): This distribution consistently achieves the lowest objective function values across the majority of functions, demonstrating excellent exploration capabilities in 10 dimensions (table 5). It seems particularly adept at navigating complex search spaces and escaping local optima. Levy (Rank 2) and Cauchy (Rank 4): These distributions show competitive performance on several functions, often coming close to the performance of Weibull. They might be valuable alternatives for specific problem landscapes. However, Tangent flight is not successful in this experiment. The same observation for the log-normal and exponential distributions.

Table 5. Mean results of 10D cec2022 function for exploration distribution flights

	Levy	Gamma	Tangent	Rayleigh	Weibull	Cauchy	Exp	Log	Chi2
Friedman rank	2	3	7	6	1	4	8	9	5
CEC1	5.750E-02	4.172E-02	1.380E-03	1.553E-02	4.730E-03	1.018E-02	1.000E-01	2.857E+01	5.221E-02
CEC2	5.180E-02	2.327E-02	6.963E-02	3.771E-02	2.135E-01	9.371E-02	4.711E-02	6.223E-01	3.462E-02
CEC3	3.811E+01	5.303E+01	5.289E+01	5.405E+01	1.018E+00	1.260E+00	5.210E+01	5.424E+01	5.245E+01
CEC4	4.296E+01	4.912E+01	4.399E+01	4.931E+01	3.884E+01	4.911E+01	4.873E+01	5.292E+01	4.339E+01
CEC5	1.072E+03	1.127E+03	1.135E+03	1.072E+03	9.284E+02	1.291E+03	1.119E+03	1.131E+03	1.195E+03
CEC6	2.101E+02	1.917E+02	2.540E+02	1.342E+02	1.286E+02	3.041E+02	3.573E+02	2.631E+02	2.187E+02
CEC7	6.293E+01	1.057E+02	8.782E+01	1.269E+02	1.243E+01	1.580E+01	1.066E+02	1.155E+02	1.062E+02
CEC8	2.414E+01	2.864E+01	2.876E+01	3.212E+01	1.927E+01	1.938E+01	2.921E+01	3.508E+01	3.086E+01
CEC9	2.215E+02	1.896E+02	2.277E+02	2.211E+02	2.212E+02	2.170E+02	2.257E+02	2.173E+02	2.122E+02
CEC10	1.217E+02	4.150E+02	2.086E+02	3.989E+02	1.529E+01	2.901E+01	5.322E+02	4.437E+02	2.906E+02
CEC11	1.089E+00	1.213E+00	1.518E+01	3.156E-01	2.044E+01	2.578E+01	2.278E+00	2.362E+01	6.334E+00
CEC12	2.166E+02	2.312E+02	2.355E+02	2.369E+02	1.687E+02	1.775E+02	2.439E+02	2.566E+02	2.389E+02

In 20D exploration (table 6), Weibull (Rank 1) stands out as the most effective distribution for exploration in 20 dimensions. Its ability to generate both short and long jumps seems to be key for navigating complex, high-dimensional landscapes effectively. Cauchy (Rank 2) and Tangent (Rank 3): These distributions perform

competitively with Weibull on several functions, showcasing their ability to explore the search space effectively. Lévy (Rank 4): While Lévy is known for its exploration prowess, it doesn't consistently outperform Weibull in this scenario. This could be attributed to the interplay between its heavy-tailed nature and the specific characteristics of the benchmark functions. Chi-Squared (Rank 5): While it performs moderately on some functions, its overall exploration capability falls behind the top performers. Rayleigh (Rank 6): Rayleigh performs moderately well across most functions but doesn't consistently reach the same level of performance as Weibull, Tangent, or Cauchy. Exponential (Rank 9), Log-Normal (Rank 7), and Gamma (Rank 8): These distributions consistently struggle in exploration, often resulting in much higher objective function values than the top performers. They might have difficulty escaping local optima or efficiently exploring the vastness of the 20-dimensional search space.

Table 6. Mean results of 20D cec2022 function for exploration distribution flights

	Levy	Gamma	Tangent	Rayleigh	Weibull	Cauchy	Exp	Log	Chi2
Friedman rank	4	8	3	6	1	2	9	7	5
CEC1	3.131E+02	1.826E+02	6.985E-02	6.802E+02	8.612E-02	3.564E-01	5.507E+00	8.834E+02	2.389E+01
CEC3	2.171E+01	2.264E+01	2.562E+01	3.245E+01	8.333E+00	1.622E+01	2.278E+01	3.352E+01	1.652E+01
CEC4	4.398E+01	7.020E+01	7.123E+01	6.898E+01	8.970E+00	2.703E+00	6.712E+01	6.758E+01	6.720E+01
CEC5	1.510E+02	1.540E+02	1.212E+02	1.463E+02	1.269E+02	1.625E+02	1.556E+02	1.451E+02	1.389E+02
CEC6	3.323E+03	3.300E+03	3.200E+03	3.322E+03	3.312E+03	3.721E+03	3.686E+03	3.259E+03	3.444E+03
CEC7	2.379E+03	1.614E+03	2.622E+02	2.463E+02	7.452E+02	1.447E+03	7.195E+03	2.215E+03	2.877E+03
CEC8	1.393E+02	2.143E+02	1.627E+02	2.206E+02	5.237E+01	6.191E+01	2.005E+02	2.093E+02	1.804E+02
CEC9	3.455E+01	7.328E+01	6.308E+01	6.974E+01	2.483E+01	2.883E+01	6.003E+01	5.626E+01	5.485E+01
CEC10	1.784E+02	1.825E+02	1.784E+02	1.858E+02	1.782E+02	1.809E+02	1.816E+02	1.874E+02	1.812E+02
CEC11	4.549E+02	2.042E+03	1.983E+03	1.907E+03	1.098E+02	4.826E+01	1.926E+03	1.921E+03	2.008E+03
CEC12	5.836E+01	2.916E+01	5.077E+01	2.167E+01	1.543E+02	5.696E+01	7.795E+01	3.041E+01	4.273E+01
CEC2	5.917E+02	8.813E+02	7.162E+02	9.536E+02	2.936E+02	3.238E+02	8.408E+02	1.021E+03	7.614E+02

The success of Weibull and Cauchy in exploration might be attributed to their ability to balance short-range movements with occasional long jumps, effectively navigating both local and global features of the search space. The Friedman rank test results provide valuable insights into the relative performance of different flight distributions across different phases of the optimization process (exploitation and exploration) and dimensionalities (10D and 20D).

Table 7 provides the statistic results of the runtime of each flight for optimization of solution of 500 dimension. The number of iterations set as 10000 and the number of runs is 30. Tangent distribution is clearly winner in terms of runtime, with the lowest mean (0.1688 seconds) and a relatively small standard deviation (0.0164 seconds). This indicates that the Tangent flight operator is computationally very efficient in this scenario. Cauchy distribution follows closely behind Tangent, with a slightly higher mean (0.1855 seconds) but a comparable standard deviation (0.0095 seconds). This suggests that Cauchy is also a computationally efficient choice. Gamma, Chi2,

Rayleigh, and Exponential exhibit moderate runtimes, falling within a similar range of 0.3 to 0.9 seconds. They offer a balance between computational efficiency and exploration/exploitation capabilities (as seen in previous results). Weibull distribution has highest mean runtime (1.238 seconds) and the largest standard deviation (0.0498 seconds). This suggests that Weibull is the most computationally expensive flight operator in this setting, likely due to the complexity of its calculations. Finally, Levy flight is the second slowest flight.

Table 7. runtime results

	mean	std	min	max
Levy	9.659E-01	2.279E-01	7.658E-01	1.586E+00
Gamma	5.706E-01	1.312E-01	4.408E-01	8.669E-01
Tangent	1.688E-01	1.640E-02	1.418E-01	2.235E-01
Rayleigh	4.140E-01	2.331E-02	3.627E-01	4.591E-01
Weibull	1.238E+00	4.983E-02	1.195E+00	1.427E+00
Cauchy	1.855E-01	9.476E-03	1.695E-01	2.111E-01
Exp	2.976E-01	1.804E-02	2.767E-01	3.768E-01
Log	3.838E-01	3.506E-02	3.625E-01	5.349E-01
Chi2	4.435E-01	4.401E-02	4.129E-01	6.430E-01

Based on the combined results from both the 10D and 20D experiments, the following distributions emerge as strong contenders:

Weibull demonstrates exceptional performance in both exploration (10D) and exploitation (20D), making it a versatile and robust choice for a wide range of optimization problems. Its ability to generate both short and long jumps seems to be key to its success in balancing exploration and exploitation. While Tangent is not as consistently top-performing as Weibull, Tangent shows good exploration capabilities in 10D and competitive exploitation performance in 20D. It could be a valuable alternative for problems with smoother landscapes or when a balance between exploration and exploitation is desired. Finally, Lévy and Cauchy are particularly strong in exploration, especially in higher dimensions. However, their performance in exploitation is less consistent. They might be best suited for problems with complex landscapes where thorough exploration is crucial.

The following table resumes the obtained results.

Table 8. summary of comparison results

Distribution	Characteristics	Strengths	Weaknesses
Lévy	Heavy-tailed, scale-free	Excellent for exploration, avoids local optima	Slow convergence, requires careful parameter tuning
Gamma	Shape parameter controls tail heaviness, versatile	Flexible for different optimization phases, good balance of exploration and exploitation	Complex parameter tuning, may not be as effective without fine-tuning

Distribution	Characteristics	Strengths	Weaknesses
Tangent	Unique shape	Provides unique step sizes, potentially beneficial in specific landscapes	Less robust
Rayleigh	Bell-shaped	Smooth steps, effective in later optimization stages	Limited exploration, better suited for local search
Weibull	Flexible shape and scale parameters	Highly adaptable, balances exploration and exploitation	Requires careful parameter tuning
Cauchy	Heavy-tailed, median-based	Capable of large jumps, effective in escaping local optima	Slow convergence, can introduce instability
Exponential	Memoryless, single parameter	Simple implementation, steady exploration	Limited broad exploration, prone to getting trapped in local optima
Log-Normal	Non-negative, skewed with long right tail	Good for modeling multiplicative processes, can handle wide range of values	Can be difficult to control, may require transformation for effective use
Chi-Square	Depends on degrees of freedom, positively skewed	Good for variance modeling, simple to implement	Not as effective for broad exploration, more suited for specific scenarios

Key Strengths of the Weibull Distribution

a) Flexibility in Shape Parameters:

The Weibull distribution is characterized by two parameters: the shape parameter k and the scale parameter λ . The shape parameter k can significantly alter the distribution's behavior:

- When $k < 1$, the distribution has a heavy tail, which promotes large exploratory jumps.
- When $k = 1$, it reduces to the exponential distribution, balancing exploration and exploitation.
- When $k > 1$, the distribution becomes more peaked around the mean, favoring smaller, more precise steps.

This flexibility allows the Weibull distribution to be tuned for different stages of the optimization process, making it highly adaptable.

b) Heavy-Tailed Nature:

The heavy tail of the Weibull distribution (when $k < 1$) means that it can occasionally take large steps. This is beneficial for escaping local optima and exploring diverse areas of the search space, which is crucial in high-dimensional optimization problems where local optima are more prevalent.

c) Balance Between Exploration and Exploitation:

The Weibull distribution's ability to adjust its shape allows it to balance exploration and exploitation effectively. In the early stages of optimization, a more exploratory shape (with a lower k) can be used. As the optimization progresses, the shape parameter can be adjusted to favor exploitation (with a higher k), leading to finer local search.

d) Robustness Across Different Dimensions:

The Weibull distribution has demonstrated robustness in both 10D and 20D scenarios. Its performance does not degrade significantly with increasing dimensionality, which is a common challenge for many optimization algorithms. This robustness is likely due to its ability to maintain a good balance between wide exploration and focused exploitation, regardless of the dimensionality.

4.2. Final recommendations

Consider Weibull as your first choice due to its overall strong performance in both exploration and exploitation across different dimensions. The choice of flight distribution involves a trade-off between exploration/exploitation performance and computational cost.

- If runtime is a critical constraint, Tangent is a strong candidate due to its efficiency. However, it might not always provide the best exploration or exploitation capabilities, as seen in previous results.
- If computational resources are not a major limitation, Weibull might be worth considering, as it has shown strong performance in certain scenarios, despite its higher runtime.
- For a balance between runtime and performance, Lévy, Rayleigh, Exponential, and Log-Normal could be good options.
- Combine distributions by sampling from a mixture to leverage strengths of different distributions over the optimization run.
- It's important to consider the specific requirements of your optimization problem and the available resources before making a decision.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we investigated the exploitation and exploration capacities of various flight distributions within population optimization algorithms. By evaluating these

capacities across different scenarios and benchmark functions, we gained valuable insights into the performance of each distribution in balancing the trade-off between exploitation and exploration.

Our findings highlight the importance of selecting appropriate flight distributions based on the characteristics of the optimization problem at hand. Weibull stands out as a versatile choice due to its exceptional performance in both exploration (searching the solution space) and exploitation (refining solutions) across different dimensions. Tangent, Levy are very successful in exploration and exploitation. Tangent emerged as the most efficient option in terms of runtime, although it may sacrifice some exploration and exploitation performance

Overall, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the role of flight distributions in population optimization algorithms. Future research directions may involve exploring hybrid approaches that leverage the strengths of multiple distributions, as well as investigating the impact of different distribution characteristics on algorithm performance. By continuing to refine and innovate in this field, we can advance the state-of-the-art in optimization and address increasingly complex real-world challenges.

References:

1. H. B. Curry, "The method of steepest descent for non-linear minimization problems," *Quarterly of Applied Mathematics*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 258–261, 1944.
2. Hestenes, M. R., & Stiefel, E. (1952). *Methods of conjugate gradients for solving linear systems*. Journal of Research of the National Bureau of Standards, 49(6), 409-436.
3. Nocedal, J., & Wright, S. J. (2006). *Numerical optimization*. Springer Science & Business Media.
4. Holland, J. H. (1992). *Adaptation in natural and artificial systems: An introductory analysis with applications to biology, control, and artificial intelligence*. MIT press.
5. Storn, R., & Price, K. (1997). Differential evolution—a simple and efficient heuristic for global optimization over continuous spaces. *Journal of global optimization*, 11(4), 341-359.
6. Kennedy, J., & Eberhart, R. (1995). Particle swarm optimization. *Proceedings of ICNN'95-international conference on neural networks*, 4, 1942-1948.
7. Dorigo, M., & Di Caro, G. (1999). Ant colony optimization: a new meta-heuristic. *Proceedings of the 1999 congress on evolutionary computation-CEC99 (Cat. No. 99TH8406)*, 2, 1470-1477.
8. Kirkpatrick, S., Gelatt, C. D., & Vecchi, M. P. (1983). Optimization by simulated annealing. *science*, 220(4598), 671-680.
9. Glover, F. (1989). Tabu search—part I. *ORSA Journal on computing*, 1(3), 190-206.
10. Talbi, E-G. (2009). *Metaheuristics: From design to implementation*. John Wiley & Sons.
11. Yang, X. S. (2010). *Engineering optimization: An introduction with metaheuristic applications*. John Wiley & Sons.
12. Eiben, A. E., & Smith, J. E. (2003). *Introduction to evolutionary computing*. Springer Science & Business Media.
13. Kirkpatrick, S., Gelatt, C. D., & Vecchi, M. P. (1983). Optimization by simulated annealing. *Science*, 220(4598), 671-680.
14. Beyer, H.-G., & Schwefel, H.-P. (2002). Evolution strategies—a comprehensive introduction. *Natural computing*, 1(1), 3-52.
15. Michalewicz, Z. (1996). *Genetic algorithms + data structures = evolution programs*. Springer Science & Business Media.
16. Nolan, J. P. (2018). *Stable distributions: Models for heavy-tailed data*. Birkhauser.

17. Walck, C. (2007). Handbook on statistical distributions for experimentalists. University of Stockholm, Internal Report SUF-PFY/96-01, 11, 1-5.
18. Layeb, A. (2022). Tangent search algorithm for solving optimization problems. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 34(11), 8853-8884. [19] Rayleigh:
19. Siddiqui, M. M. (1962). Some problems connected with Rayleigh distributions. *Journal of Research of the National Bureau of Standards D*, 66, 167-174.
20. Rinne, H. (2009). *The Weibull distribution: a handbook*. CRC Press.
21. Layeb, A. (2024). Differential evolution algorithms with novel mutations, adaptive parameters, and Weibull flight operator. *Soft Computing*, 1-53.
22. Johnson, N. L., Kotz, S., & Balakrishnan, N. (1994). *Continuous univariate distributions (Vol. 1)*. Wiley-Interscience.
23. Forbes, C., Evans, M., Hastings, N., & Peacock, B. (2011). *Statistical distributions*. John Wiley & Sons.
24. Crow, E. L., & Shimizu, K. (Eds.). (1988). *Lognormal distributions: Theory and applications (Vol. 88)*. CRC Press.
25. Lancaster, H. O. (1969). *The chi-squared distribution*. Wiley.
26. Kumar, A.; Price, K.; Mohamed, A.; Hadi, A.; Suganthan, P.N. Problem Definitions and Evaluation Criteria for the CEC 2022 Special Session and Competition on Single Objective Bound Constrained Numerical Optimization; Technical Report; Nanyang Technological University: Singapore, 2021.

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